

Role of Tourism in Women’s Empowerment

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ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History

Published Online: 30 July 2018

Keywords

Women empowerment, Women, Tourism Industry

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ABSTRACT

Tourism is one of the largest Industry in the world. The Industry is constructing and contributing world’s economic power. The evolution of Tourism is not only benefiting the country’s economic but also strengthening human development such as poverty mitigation, Women empowerment etc. Women empowerment is the wild problem in the 21st century, facing by all over the World. Women empowerment is creating opportunities to make their own decision in their family, society, workstation, etc., In order to eradicate gender discrimination among men and Women, many countries have been taken several efforts with the help of internal and external collaboration of organizations. Many laws have been implemented by the government to find out the solution for Women empowerment. Tourism Industry is also showing several path to Women’s empowerment widely. Tourism Industry is establishing opportunities for living with self-confidence, self-respect, dignity and providing proper education to Women. As compared to other organization, Tourism Industry have huge number of Women employees. The objective of the paper is to examine the parameters involve to cause Women’s empowerment through Tourism Industry. This is conceptual based study, has taken with the intention of examining the influence of Tourism Industry in Women’s empowerment. This study is based on secondary data analysis. Information have been collected from several websites, online journals, online news and articles etc.

1. Introduction

The word Women empowerment refers to upgrading and developing the political, economic, social and authorized strength of the Women, to achieve equal right for Women, and in accordance to claim their rights and to create them more confident. Gender inequality is the important hurdle in several nations. The international Women’s empowerment year has been declared in the year 2001 by the United Nations (UN) in order to honor every Women in the world. The significant mode for empowering Women is Tourism. Creating job opportunity is one of the main track to strengthen the economic status, Tourism creates various job opportunities for Women. Various Tourism allied organizations are enhancing to enrich the status of Women in the society.

IIPIT India (International Institute for peace through Tourism – India) organized Women’s day events at the ITB (Internationale Tourismus-Börse Berlin), Berlin. The High spot of the event was inspiring discussion and celebrating “Her Awards”. From the travel & Tourism, In order to motivate and to honor 5 magnificent Women every year those Women have empowered themselves and help others also to empower. The winners of the celebrating HER award for the year 2018 are: for utilizing Tourism to Tourism Communities, Sandra Howard Taylor, Vice Minister of Tourism, Colombia won the award. For the purpose of constructing universal agreement to promote Tourism as an energy for good and Caroline Bremner, head of travel research, Euro monitors International who had won the award for travel research and education. Jyotsna Suri, Managing Director and Chairperson of Lalit Hotels, India won the award for the purpose of Tourism leadership.

2. Conceptual framework for Role of Tourism in Women empowerment:

3. Opportunities Generated by Tourism Industry to Women

In the 21st century, a necessity has raised on the concept of gender perspective in the discussions of the Tourism Industry. The discussions about Women’s employment in the industry. Tourism opened several gates for Women and assist them in providing remuneration by involving them in Tourism events, hence it builds their status in societies. The Global report on Women in Tourism, 2010, the report insists to stimulate empowerment and protection of Women and their rights by Tourism job. Five goals have been set up to equal employment opportunities for Women in Tourism, to create more Women entrepreneurs in Tourism, to develop their skills and knowledge through education, to inspire Women to guide in Tourism, to provide protection to the defenseless Women and those Women who engage them in Tourism home based companies. As per Ministry of Tourism report, India, says Tourism is an Industry with an occurrence of Women. Tourism Industry is creating knowledge and providing skills through Tourism education, placing them in job, producing business opportunities and growing leadership qualities in Women, offering home based work indirectly and increasing Women’s involvement in Tourism events.

4. Tourism Education

To supply and meet the demand of skilled person in hospitality industries, many diploma courses, degree courses and doctoral courses have been introduced. As per the article 21 of Indian constitution, speaks about providing education without any gender discrimination. SarvaShikshaAbhiyan supports girl's education. Tourism Industry also opens the gate of education to Women without any gender discrimination. Latin, America is providing training for Women in the service sector. Diageo is a beverage alcohol company with several brands. Diageo products are purchased by 180 countries all around the world. Plan W is the one of the foremost goal of Diageo for the year 2020. The aim of the Plan W is to empower Women by providing education and equip them with skill and it leads to support economy and society. In 2013, Diageo signed the UN Women's empowerment worldwide to empower Women by offering chances to grow in their skill, competences and aptitudes. One of the main aim of the Plan W is to improve knowledge and skills of the Women and providing training to them to place in job or to engage in business. 90,575 Women are empowered through learning by Plan W and it is indirectly influenced by 452,875 people across 15 nations. In India, in order to promote Tourism education, introduced 1 year course PG Diploma course in Travel and Tourism Management course in South Delhi Polytechnic for Women, PG Diploma course in Tourism Management in SNDT Women's University, Mumbai. Introduced Bachelor course in Tourism Management for the duration of 4 years in Mother Teresa Women's University, Kodaikanal. Madagascar is the most economically challenged and poorest country in the world with the 8% of population, situated in the Western Indian Ocean in the continent Africa. UNESCO's (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization) CapED is a Vocational education and training programme engaged with the partnership of Foundation CHANEL in 2018, January. The programme prosperous the local community who have their habitant in the tourist destination and World heritage site of UNESCO named Tsingy Nature Reserve, situated at Western coast of Madagascar. The partnership ties expertise from Educational sector and UNESCO culture. To prosperous Women, develop their livelihood and to make them to lead their life independently in finance and with confidence, training and occasions in sustainable Tourism. These two vocational programs supports in both aspects are local produce and sustainable Tourism. The training is provided to six hundred Women and it helps them in selling vegetables to hotels and local handicrafts with tradition are produced and marketed by Women. The Ministry of Tourism in India makes Women representatives and officers to take part in numerous training programme to construct their capability. Arts and crafts is also one of the attraction of the tourist, to encourage that, WELL (Women Empowered through Local Livelihood), established by two Israel personalities Danny and OrlyMerguei in Pondichery, India. The foremost aim of the WELL is to empower local habitant Women to construct their skills, achieve and sustain. Training would be provided in the field of market and team management, personal management and product development. Training were provided to 40 Women in Kannyakumari, India for four 4 months training on 'Integrated Design and Technical Development Project on Natural Fibre Craft'.

5. Employment Opportunities

According to the WTTC report, In 2013, the industry provided 101 million jobs. As per the report of WTTC (World Tourism and Travel Council) on the role of Women in the Tourism Industry, Tourism is the fundamental industry for Women employment. Tourism Industry is creating enormous opportunities to the Women with the respect of empowering Women. While comparing with other industries, Tourism is the only industry, give opportunity to at least one Women as Tourism minister among 5 Tourism ministers in worldwide. In 1st August 2015, Dr. Fang Lio was employed as first female secretary general for the UN agency's Secretariat and in 2018, she has appointed as secretary general of ICAO (International Civil Aviation Organization). In the Seventh session on sustainable development conducted in 1999, April, CSD (Commission on Sustainable Development). But the project originated in 1998, September between UNED-UK. The project known as "Gender & Tourism: Women's Employment and Participation in Tourism", The main goal of the project is gender phases of Tourism to the consideration of policymaker's, particularly the problem of Tourism generating employment for Women and their involvement in Tourism planning and management. The project report says about the worldwide condition of Women employees in the Tourism Industry and participation of Women. These aspects are submitted through 12 case studies. The Industry dedicates several openings for Women to lead their lives independently with the income. The project inspected the number of Women workers in the Tourism Industry universally for the past 10 years. The inspection includes their average rate of wage and their working hours of Women with the comparison of men. The allied industries such as restaurant, catering and hotel industry, creating more opportunities overall. The common image proposes, Women workforce are 46%. A Women named Adrienne Lee, who serves her service to the tour operator industry called Planeterra as Director of Development. Regarding the report of WTTC on EU (European Union), It is found by Euro stat, 36% of employees are female, Females are involved more in Tourism Industry as labor force, it secured 58% involvement by Women. In the accommodation industry, highest proportion of Women employment is 60%. And in the field of travel agency and tour operator, Women occupied 64%. In the EU member states like Belgium, Luxemburg and Malta, Women employment was less than 50%. In the accommodation sector, countries like Poland and Slovakia, female employment double the time increased and secured 67%. Degree courses in Tourism and Travel Management is available and lady lecturers have been appointed to teach Women students. Women have more scope in airline industries, they render their services as air hostesses, air ticketing etc. Abraham path project has been developed by WBG (World Bank Group), the aim of the project is to take care of community based Tourism with the historic Abraham path. The other aim of the project is to create Tourism income and occupation and development in Women's economic chances. The Small Scale Innovative project is introduced in 2014. The project has created 137 jobs, on that 57% has occupied by Women. Indian Ministry of Tourism is allotted seats for 186 Women employees in ITDC (India Tourism Development Corporation) between the year 2016-2017. Women officials have appointed in regional offices and also overseas offices in the Ministry of Tourism.

6. Business Opportunity

In most of the regions, Women are owning and running several businesses such as handicrafts business, accommodation providers (Break fast, bed etc.) are often female operator. According to the report of Oxford Economics and World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), Tourism is the industry offers several self-employment opportunities to Women in high proportion while comparing with other industry. These reports analyzed and gathered information in 5 countries like Australia, France, Germany, South Africa and Turkey. Women plays their role as Entrepreneurs, leaders in business. As per the UNWTO (United Nations World Tourism Organization), Women employers are more in number in a few countries. When comparing with 20% in other sector, In Tourism Industry in the countries such as Nicaragua and Panama, Women employers are more than 70%. From the report of UNWTO, in Tourism Industry, it is found that voices of Women in Tourism businesses, strong relationship and Tourism administering skills than in other sector. The 2010, Global report on Women in Tourism, reveals Women employers are more in hotel and restaurant industry as compared to other industries. Tourism generates more informal and home based businesses for Women when comparing with other fields. It gives opportunity to run and sustain in small scale businesses such as owing hotels and restaurant, petty shops, small factory etc. for local Women community. Craft is one the attraction for tourist. Craft is an creative idea of Women. These crafts also paves the way to start up the business with less investment and to strengthen their financial position. In Karnataka, there is a district called Shimoga, The place is well known for art style called Gudigar works. Sandal wood is used in this style of art with ivory carving. The Women in the place are more proficient in making garlands with the skinny layer of sandal. In India, Manipur is the state, surrounded with the Mountains. Manipur is also considered as Switzerland. Black pottery is an ancient crafts. Linkages of businesspersons and universal connectivity, ensures black pottery to bring into markets inside India and all over the world. The existence of black pottery in the market supports the local female artisans to gain revenue and secure new identification in their family and villages. Village handicrafts is one of the informal economic division. As per International Labor Organization, around 50 of 40 million are home-based worker are Women in South Asia. Shilpotsav is an arts and crafts celebration by Women artisans in Karnataka. During the celebration a wide range of Indian arts and crafts like Pottery, painting, Paper arts, Ceramics, wood carving, leather lampshades, embroideries, terracotta stuffs etc from different states would be exhibited by Women in the exhibition in Bengaluru. The initiative of the celebration is taken by Karnataka Chitrakala Parishath in Bengaluru. Rajasthan is familiar for its rich and colorful arts and crafts. Sunder Rang means "Beautiful Colour". The building known as Sunder Rang, it is meant for arts & crafts project. The Sunder Rang creates opportunities for the Women of Chandelao in the aspect of creating handicrafts of Rajasthan. The main objective of Sunder Rang is to aid and conserve the Rajasthan's crafts and to produce high worth products with specific designs of Rajasthan. Hence it generates standard revenue to the Chandelao's Women. Nearly 30 Women are working in Sunder Rang to Rajasthan's traditional handicrafts and fabric, and those are consumed inside and outside India. Pondicherry is a territorial

region, situated in Southern part of India. WELL (Women's Empowerment through Local Livelihood) is a non-profit organization in Pondicherry, originated in the 2005 with the two primary motives of contributing self-employment and standard livelihood for Women. They produce WELL paper products and encourage recycled materials, hence it is called environmental aware project. In Kanniyakumari, district administration has arranged loan for Women to commence business in the concern of handicrafts. 30 sort of handicraft products are manufactured in Kanniyakumari in India. The value of those handicrafts are Rs. 15 Crore and exports to several countries like Australia, Japan, France, Italy, Germany, USA, Canada and Arabia. In Rajasthan, India, A Women called SumitaGose, after many difficulties and constraints, she started a company known 'Rang Sutra'. Rang Sutra is the company based on handicrafts. The handicraft company is functioning with 3000 artisans from interior villages and areas across India. This company is running with 70% of Women artisan members. The organization is well-versed in manufacturing embroidery, tie-dye, applique, engineered weaving, handloom weaving, extra weft weaving, silver jewelry and beads. Raghurajpur is a village in Odisha, is the best example for treasure of culture. Raghurajpur is the village which have 300 artisans includes Women. 300 artisans are Pattachitra painters includes Women. Pattachitra is the form of painting, used to paint along with a piece of cloth, dried palm leaf and with a mixture of chalk and gum. The front room and space of the every houses are decorated with paintings using several attractive colours, People in Raghurajpur is reserved for exhibition purpose but not for commercial reason. The men and Women in the house explains their tradition and narrate about the paintings in Odiya. Orissa are bonded with arts and crafts. The State is awarded for identifying and encouraging craftsmen and the awards like National Merit Certificate, National Award, Padma Bushan and padmashree award. Some of the prominent crafts are golden grass work of Cuttak, wood and stone craving of Puri, Paralakhemundi's horn work, Mayurbhanj's Dhokra work, Barapally's clay toys etc.

7. Conclusion

After analyzing the parameters such as Tourism education, employment opportunity, business opportunity and Women's involvement in Tourism events ensures that Tourism Industry have been generated enormous ways to obtain Tourism education. Introducing several courses, degrees etc. Many training and development programs have been introduced to develop their skills. Opening numerous employment opportunities for various services in hotels, airlines, Institutions, Tourism offices, travel agent, Tourism information centers etc. Some Women have been placed as higher authority in the Tourism field. Indian government have been reserved seats for Women's employment in Tourism Industry. In many educational institutions, Women are working as professors. Tourism Industry is supporting self-employment for Women. Significantly, many Women are operating their own hotels, small scale industries etc. Several handicrafts business are flourishing by Women in India. Many training centers have been emerged to enhance their skills and to learn. It paves the way to launch their new business. Their craft skills are the best illustration for their innovation and tremendous creation. Tourism Industry have been generated home based work for Women. Involvement in cultural activities like fairs & festivals and other

events, relevant to Tourism also shows their attentiveness and their capability. Hence this, the Tourism Industry in the world, is playing a dynamic and vibrant role in Women empowerment by

providing revenue, make Women to stand and face the world with confidence and courageous.

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